
MOST IMPORTANT ISSUES REGARDING ESP MATERIALS SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is generally defined as an approach to learning English which is based on the goals/needs of the learner. In context learning English at both high schools and universities, especially for students outside the English department, the ESP approach is a popular choice. The application of this approach is also in line with government policies in education which emphasize the objectives of learning English, namely to improve the ability of students to use English, especially for academic needs and professional careers with an emphasis on reading skills that allow students to understand authentic material topics according to their majors.

Keywords: *ESP, method, assessment, issue, field, criteria, language, course, learners, adequacy, motivation, sequence, diversity.*

English for specific purposes (ESP) teaching conducted to equip learners with a certain English proficiency level for a situation where the language is going to be used, termed target needs. Since it provides instructional objectives, materials and methods developed on the basis of earners' needs and potential of interests, from the early 1960s, ESP has grown to become one of the most prominent areas of English foreign language. Nowadays, ESP is not only applied for adults of English language learners who have mastered basic level of English proficiency or those with specific purposes of learning English, but also is adopted for English language learners learning general English.

Many definitions are given to ESP. Some people describe ESP as simply being the teaching of English for any purpose that could be specified. Others, however, are more precise, describing it as the teaching of English used in academic studies or the teaching of English for vocational or professional purposes, or as the teaching of English for nonnative speakers of English who learn English on specific purposes.

Hutchinson & Waters define ESP as an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learners' reason in learning [Hutchinson & Waters, 1987:19]. Robinson viewed ESP as an enterprise involving education, training, and practice and drawing upon three major realisms of knowledge namely language, pedagogy, and students'/participants' specialist area of interest [Robinson,1991:1]. Richards & Rodger saw ESP as a movement that seeks to serve the language needs of learners who need English in order to carry out specific roles (e.g. student, engineer, nurse) and who need to acquire content and real-world skills through the medium of it rather than master the language for its own sake [Richards & Rodger (2001:107)]. The more detail definition of ESP comes from Strevens (1998) who defined ESP as a particular case of general category of special purpose language teaching. He further revealed that the definition of ESP is needed to distinguish between four absolute and two variable characteristics. The four absolute characteristics of ESP consist of English language teaching, they are The definition given by Dudley-Evanthat consists of three absolute and five variable characteristics, represents an insight that ESP can but is not necessarily concerned with a specific discipline, nor it does have to be aimed at a certain age group or ability range. It simply should be seen as an approach to teaching, or what Dudley-Evans describes as an 'attitude of mind'. This is a similar assumption to that proposed by Hutchinson & Waters who state that ESP is an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner's reason for learning [Hutchinson & Waters, 1987:19].

The meaning of the word 'special' in ESP more confirms the rule of ESP as an approach to language teaching in which content and method applied based on the learner's need of learning. In the other words, a specialized aim refers to the purpose for which learners learn a language, not the nature of the language they learn [Mackay & Mountford, 1978]. Consequently, as an approach, ESP has typically functioned to help language learners cope with the features of language or to develop the competencies needed to function in a discipline, profession, or workplace for which the learners want to master English. In the context of teaching English in Indonesia both at secondary and tertiary school levels, particularly for non-English department students, ESP approach has been commonly applied. This is in accordance with the Government policy on Education that emphasizes the goal of teaching English at tertiary school level, especially for non-English department students, is to improve their ability to use English for academic and professional

purposes, especially for reading their textbooks in their academic work. This implies that in the English language instruction, reading skill has been given the greatest prominence for helping students to learn effectively in their field of study. It is also related to what Hutchinson & Waters state that the specific purpose most common within the participant universities is the reading of specialist literature in English, and the emphasis is largely on a general course content to cover common problems, such as reading strategies, rather than specific discourses, according to the student subject specialism. For this purpose, they further explain that as the consequence, there is a consensus within the teaching and learning process to focus on the teaching of reading strategies with the use of authentic materials and the use of the native language in spoken classroom discourse, while the teaching of grammar is based on the minimum necessary for understanding academic texts.

Therefore, based on this approach, even reading is the most emphasized skill in the English instruction, other language skills namely speaking, listening, and writing will also take place with the components of language are incorporated in it. Methodology refers to the selection and sequencing of learning tasks and activities to achieve the desired instructional objective. Methodology is also defined as what students have to do. This clearly has the implication of what the teacher has to do and what materials are used. Robinson identifies two characteristics features of ESP methodology that ESP can base activities on students specialism (but need not to do so) and ESP activities can (but may not) have a truly authentic purpose derived from students' target. Dudley-Evans & St. John maintain that what characterizes ESP methodology is the use of tasks and activities reflecting the students' specialist areas.

Todd reports that six approaches have been emphasized in the EAP literature: inductive learning, process syllabuses, learner autonomy, use of authentic materials and tasks, integration of teaching and technology and team teaching (cooperating with content teachers). Todd argues that whereas the first five are also found in general English language teaching, the sixth, team teaching or cooperation with content teachers, is distinctive to EAP. Robinson states that the common instructional tasks in ESP course are role-play, simulation, case-study, project work, and oral presentation by which the instruction effectively promotes communication and professional skill as well as language skills of students [Robinson, 1991:49].

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